

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o^}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^University of Bari Aldo Moro

Seat-Km Offered by Local Public Transport in Italian Regions

Decreased by 27% on Average Between 2004 and 2021

Istat calculates the value of seat-km offered by local public transport in Italian regions. The variable is defined as the product of the total number of km actually traveled in the year by all public transport vehicles by the average capacity of the vehicles in service, related to the total number of residents (seat-km per inhabitant).

Trend of Seat-Km Offered by Local Public Transport in Italian Regions in 2021. The analysis of data on "seat-km offered by local public transport" in Italian regions for the year 2020 shows significant variation in the capacity of local public transport offered to residents. This variation reflects not only differences in population density and geographical extent of the regions but also different political priorities and investment levels in public transport. Lombardy emerges as the region with the highest value of seat-km offered, reaching 9109. This can be attributed to the high population density, significant industrial and commercial fabric, and the presence of Milan, a crucial transport hub in Italy and Europe. This suggests a well-developed local public transport system, likely capable of effectively meeting the mobility needs of the population. Conversely, regions such as Molise and Basilicata show the lowest values, at 383 and 801 respectively, indicating lower public transport capacity. This can be due to various factors, including lower population density, less urban development, or lower investments in the public transport sector. These differences highlight the importance of targeted regional strategies to improve the accessibility and efficiency of public transport. Tourist regions such as Trentino-Alto Adige and Sardinia present intermediate values, at 3287 and 2424 respectively, reflecting the need for adequate offerings to support both the resident population and tourist flows. This shows how mobility needs can vary significantly not only based on demographic characteristics but also on economic and social factors. In conclusion, the analysis of seat-km offered by local public transport in Italy in 2020 highlights the challenges and opportunities in the public transport sector. It emphasizes the importance of sustainable mobility policies that consider regional specificities and aim to reduce disparities, improving the quality and accessibility of public transport services across all Italian regions. This will not only promote greater

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

territorial equity but also contribute to the transition towards more sustainable and inclusive mobility systems.

Trend of Seat-Km Offered by Local Public Transport in Italian Regions Between 2004 and 2021. The analysis of data on "seat-km offered by local public transport" in Italian regions between 2004 and 2021 shows a general trend of decreasing public transport capacity in many regions, with significant percentage variations reflecting substantial changes in transport capacity offered to residents. Piemonte, Liguria, and Lombardy, although among the most industrialized and densely populated regions, recorded a decrease in capacity, though to a lesser extent for Lombardy (-0.23%), suggesting relative stability in public transport capacity in this region. Valle d'Aosta and Basilicata experienced the most marked reductions, with percentage variations of -50% and -59.15% respectively, indicating a significant contraction in public transport capacity that could negatively affect resident mobility and service accessibility. Particularly concerning is the case of Campania, which saw a decrease in capacity of over 55%, the highest in absolute terms (-1781). This could have significant repercussions on the quality of life of citizens, especially in densely populated metropolitan areas like Naples and its surroundings, where public transport demand is high. On the other hand, Lombardy showed notable resilience in public transport capacity, with almost no variation. This could be attributed to continuous investments in the improvement and expansion of local public transport services, as well as the central role Milan and its metropolitan area play in the Italian and European economy. The reductions observed in regions such as Umbria, Marche, and Lazio are also significant, with Lazio recording a decrease of over 38%, highlighting significant challenges in managing public transport capacity in regions with large urban centers like Rome. In conclusion, the period between 2004 and 2021 saw a general decrease in "seat-km" capacity offered by local public transport in Italy, with some regions experiencing particularly severe cuts. This trend raises important questions about the sustainability of urban and regional mobility, the accessibility of services, and the environmental impact of the potential increase in private vehicle use.

Italian Macro-Regions Between 2004 and 2021. The analysis of data on "seat-km offered by local public transport" in Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021 reveals a trend of decreasing local public transport capacity on a national scale, with variations reflecting complex regional dynamics and specific challenges. The overall percentage variation for Italy shows a reduction of -24.11%, indicating a significant contraction in public transport capacity during the period considered. Central Italy is particularly affected, with a percentage variation of -37.03%, indicating a sharp reduction in public transport capacity. This could reflect economic difficulties, transport policy choices, or the impact of external events that may have influenced investment and management of local public transport services in these regions. Even more pronounced is the decrease observed in the Mezzogiorno and the Islands, with variations of -43.65% and -45.34% respectively. These data highlight the issue of territorial disparity in Italy, with southern and insular regions experiencing the most severe reductions in public transport capacity. This phenomenon could exacerbate mobility difficulties, limiting access to essential services and economic opportunities for residents of these areas. Northern Italy presents a less drastic but still significant situation, with the North-West and North-East recording decreases of -6.56% and -21.04% respectively. The less pronounced reduction in the North-West might reflect greater resilience in public transport capacity. These data reveal the challenges Italy faces in ensuring an equitable and sustainable local public transport capacity across all its regions. The decrease in local public transport capacity, particularly in Central Italy, the

Mezzogiorno, and the Islands, calls attention to the need for targeted investments and inclusive policies that can revitalize public transport services, reducing regional disparities and promoting accessible mobility for all citizens. Commitment to sustainable mobility and innovation in transport services could be a crucial lever to address these challenges, improving quality of life and supporting equitable and sustainable economic development across all Italian macro-regions.

North-South Divide. The analysis of "seat-km offered by local public transport" in Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021 highlights a significant divide between the North and the South of the country, revealing disparities in access to and quality of local public transport services. This divide is evident through a less marked reduction in public transport capacity in northern regions compared to southern and insular regions, where the decreases were much more significant, with percentage variations exceeding 40% in many areas. This situation reflects not only the endemic economic and infrastructural challenges in Southern Italy but also the unequal distribution of investments in essential public services like local public transport. The higher population density and economic dynamism of the North have favored greater and more consistent investments in local public transport, supporting more efficient and extensive public transport networks. Conversely, the South, characterized by lower urban density and a more fragile economic base, faces more severe limitations in financing and maintaining adequate public transport capacity. This imbalance not only underscores the need for targeted policies to improve the accessibility and efficiency of local public transport in southern and insular regions but also highlights the importance of addressing the structural roots of the North-South divide to promote more equitable and sustainable development across the national territory.

Conclusions. Between 2004 and 2021, the value of the seat-km variable in Italian regions decreased by an average of 27.06%. Significant reductions also occurred at the macro-regional level, with southern regions showing very high levels of reduction in the seat-km ratio. It should be considered that a significant role in the reduction of this variable could be due to the privatization of many local public transport services. To increase the seat-km offered by Local Public Transport (LPT) in Italian regions, it is necessary to adopt targeted economic policies supported by significant public investments and technological innovation. A priority action is to increase public investments to expand and modernize the vehicle fleet and improve existing infrastructure, funded through state budgets, European funds, and public-private partnerships. Equally essential is to encourage sustainable mobility through tax incentives, fare reductions for users, and the creation of limited traffic zones. The integration between urban planning and LPT development, involving close collaboration between government entities at all levels, would facilitate service accessibility and promote intermodality. The adoption of innovative technologies, such as electronic ticketing systems and the introduction of eco-friendly vehicles, can make LPT more efficient and attractive, while also contributing to long-term operating cost reductions. Public-private partnerships represent another tool to combine the management efficiency of the private sector with public financial support, especially for large-scale projects or the adoption of frontier technologies. It is also crucial to leverage funds dedicated to the ecological transition, such as those provided by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, to invest in LPT that supports low-emission mobility. Finally, the importance of training and developing the skills of workers in the sector should not be overlooked, as it is essential for improving service quality and adapting to innovations.

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1-20.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Appendix

Posti-km offerti dal TPL nelle regioni italiane - 2020

Posti-km offerti dal TPL nelle regioni italiane (2004 vs 2020) e Variazione Percentuale